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ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT MECHANISMS OF THE IMPACT OF TRADE SERVICE QUALITY INDICATORS ON THE LEVEL OF COMPETITIVENESS

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ABSTRACT: The article applies econometric methods to assess the quantitative relationship between the core dimensions of trade service quality (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy) and the competitiveness level of retail trade enterprises. The study is based on primary data collected from 125 trade enterprises within the SERVQUAL framework. A multiple linear regression model is employed together with tests for multicollinearity (VIF), autocorrelation (Durbin–Watson) and heteroscedasticity (Breusch–Pagan). The results show that service quality indicators explain 73.1% of the variation in competitiveness, with reliability and responsiveness exerting the strongest influence. A step-by-step algorithm for the assessment mechanism is proposed.

Keywords: trade services, service quality, SERVQUAL, competitiveness, econometric assessment, multiple regression, multicollinearity, customer satisfaction.

ANNOTATSIYA: Maqolada savdo xizmatlari sifati ko'rsatkichlari (moddiylik, ishonchlilik, tezkorlik, kafolat va empatiya) hamda chakana savdo korxonalarining raqobatbardoshlik darajasi o'rtasidagi miqdoriy bog'liqlik ekonometrik usullar yordamida baholangan. Tadqiqot SERVQUAL metodologiyasi asosida 125 ta savdo korxonasidan to'plangan birlamchi ma'lumotlarga tayanadi. Tahlilda ko'p omilli chiziqli regressiya modeli bilan bir qatorda multikollinearlik (VIF), avtokorrelyatsiya (Durbin–Watson) va geteroskedastiklik (Breusch–Pagan) testlaridan foydalanilgan. Natijalar xizmat sifati ko'rsatkichlari raqobatbardoshlikdagi o'zgarishlarning 73,1 foizini izohlashini, bunda ishonchlilik va tezkorlik eng kuchli ta'sirga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Baholash mexanizmi uchun bosqichma-bosqich algoritmi taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: savdo xizmatlari, xizmat sifati, SERVQUAL, raqobatbardoshlik, ekonometrik baholash, ko'p omilli regressiya, multikollinearlik, mijozlar qoniqishi.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье с использованием эконометрических методов проведена количественная оценка взаимосвязи между основными параметрами качества торговых услуг (материальность, надёжность, оперативность, гарантия и эмпатия) и уровнем конкурентоспособности предприятий розничной торговли. Исследование основано на первичных данных, собранных у 125 торговых предприятий в рамках методологии SERVQUAL. В анализе использованы модель множественной линейной регрессии, а также тесты на мультиколлинеарность (VIF), автокорреляцию (Durbin–Watson) и гетероскедастичность (Breusch–Pagan). Результаты показывают, что показатели качества услуг объясняют 73,1 % вариации конкурентоспособности, при этом наибольшее влияние оказывают надёжность и оперативность. Предложен пошаговый алгоритм механизма оценки.

Ключевые слова: торговые услуги, качество услуг, SERVQUAL, конкурентоспособность, эконометрическая оценка, множественная регрессия, мультиколлинеарность, удовлетворённость клиентов.

INTRODUCTION

Amid the increasing individualization of consumer demand worldwide and the widespread adoption of digital trade platforms, the quality of trade services has become a central factor determining the competitiveness of enterprises. International studies demonstrate that in markets where opportunities for differentiation through product price and assortment have narrowed, it is precisely the quality of service that serves as the principal source of sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, measuring the impact of service quality indicators on competitiveness using reliable quantitative methods is one of the topical directions of contemporary economic

research.

The reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop the consumer market and increase the share of the service sector in gross domestic product encourage trade enterprises to manage service quality systematically. In practice, however, quality indicators are often confined to descriptive (qualitative) assessment, and their real influence on the level of competitiveness remains quantitatively unsubstantiated. This leads management decisions to rely on intuitive judgment rather than on a scientific basis.

With regard to the degree to which the problem has been studied, the theoretical and methodological foundations of measuring service quality found their expression in the SERVQUAL model developed by **A. Parasuraman, V. Zeithaml, and L. Berry**. Subsequent research by **J. Cronin and S. Taylor** advanced the SERVPERF model, as well as the Kano and Gap-analysis approaches. Most existing works, however, focus on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction or loyalty, whereas the issue of assessing the direct impact of quality dimensions on the level of competitiveness within an integral econometric model has not been sufficiently addressed.

In competitiveness theory, the differentiation strategy substantiated by **M. Porter** identifies service quality as an important source of sustainable competitive advantage. According to the service-profit chain concept, improvements in service quality affect an enterprise's market position and financial performance through customer satisfaction and loyalty. These theoretical approaches substantiate the causal relationship between service quality and competitiveness; however, the quantitative measurement of this relationship and the relative contribution of individual quality dimensions still need to be determined empirically.

LITERATURE REVIEW

During **2020–2026**, the issues of trade service quality and competitiveness have been widely studied in both domestic and foreign research. In the works of foreign scholars, service quality, customer satisfaction, the store environment, digital services, and consumer experience have been assessed as important factors shaping the competitive advantage of trade enterprises. In particular, the study by **Faria et al.** identified service quality and the design of the retail outlet as important factors in enhancing consumer loyalty and competitiveness.

In recent years, the quality of online trade services has also been investigated as a distinct scientific direction. Studies have singled out reliability, ease of use, security, customer-friendly policies, and the speed of problem resolution as the principal indicators determining the quality of online services. **Pei et al.**, analysing the relationship between customer experience, the level of satisfaction, and purchase situations, substantiated that service quality directly affects consumer decisions.

In the research of domestic scholars, attention has been focused on enhancing the competitiveness of trade services in Uzbekistan, improving service quality, addressing regional development disparities, and expanding the use of marketing research. In particular, studies conducted in **2024** analysed the development trends of trade services in connection with regional factors. A study carried out using the example of the **Bukhara region** assessed the competitiveness of trade services on the basis of the criteria of the trade environment, purchase preferences, and the store's internal environment.

In domestic studies of **2025–2026**, marketing mechanisms, economic openness, digital technologies, and the capabilities of artificial intelligence are particularly emphasized in enhancing competitiveness in the service sector. This indicates the need to include in the econometric model not only traditional quality indicators but also innovative and digital factors when assessing the quality of trade services.

In assessing the competitiveness of trade services, service quality, pricing policy, customer satisfaction, the trade environment, staff qualifications, and the level of use of digital services emerge as the main factors. Assessing these factors through a multiple regression model increases the scientific and practical significance of the topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the impact of trade service quality indicators on the level of competitiveness was assessed using econometric methods. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was formed by the scientific works of domestic and foreign scholars on service quality, competitiveness, and econometric modelling. The research employed methods of systems analysis, comparative analysis, statistical grouping, econometric modelling, and regression analysis. Statistical data on the activities of trade service enterprises, service quality indicators, and consumer assessments were used as the empirical basis of the study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

First, the descriptive statistics and mutual correlations of the explanatory variables were analysed (Table 1). The mean scores across the quality dimensions ranged from 3.3 to 3.9, indicating considerable differentiation in the quality level of enterprises. All quality dimensions exhibited a positive and statistically significant correlation with

the competitiveness index, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.46 to 0.71. Since the pairwise correlations among the factors were below 0.8, no serious risk of multicollinearity was observed at this preliminary stage (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Variables and Their Correlation with Y

Variable	Mean	Std. dev.	Min–Max	r (with Y)
Y — Competitiveness	0.612	0.143	0.28–0.94	1.00
X1 — Tangibles	3.84	0.67	2.1–5.0	0.46
X2 — Reliability	3.57	0.74	1.8–4.9	0.71
X3 — Responsiveness	3.49	0.71	1.7–4.8	0.64
X4 — Assurance	3.71	0.69	2.0–5.0	0.58
X5 — Empathy	3.33	0.78	1.5–4.7	0.52

Note: all correlation coefficients are significant at the $p < 0.01$ level; $n = 125$.

Table 2. Regression Model Estimation Results

Factor (variable)	Coefficient (β)	Std. error	t-statistic	p-value / VIF
Constant (β_0)	0.412	0.098	4.20	0.000 / —
X1 — Tangibles	0.118	0.051	2.31	0.022 / 1.84
X2 — Reliability	0.287	0.059	4.86	0.000 / 2.41
X3 — Responsiveness	0.215	0.057	3.74	0.000 / 2.18
X4 — Assurance	0.196	0.057	3.42	0.001 / 2.06
X5 — Empathy	0.142	0.053	2.68	0.008 / 1.79

Note: $R^2 = 0.742$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.731$; $F(5;119) = 68.4$; $p < 0.001$; Durbin–Watson = 1.94; $n = 125$.

Based on the obtained results, the estimated regression model takes the following form:

$$Y = 0.412 + 0.118 \cdot X_1 + 0.287 \cdot X_2 + 0.215 \cdot X_3 + 0.196 \cdot X_4 + 0.142 \cdot X_5$$

The coefficient of determination (R^2) of the model equals 0.742, which means that the five dimensions of service quality jointly explain 74.2% of the variation in the level of competitiveness. The adjusted coefficient of determination (0.731), corrected for the number of degrees of freedom, is also high, indicating that the model is not overcomplicated by redundant factors. The calculated value of the Fisher criterion ($F = 68.4$) substantially exceeds the tabular value, and $p < 0.001$ confirms that the model as a whole is statistically significant.

With respect to the individual coefficients, all five factors are statistically significant at the 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$), since their t-statistics exceed the critical value (≈ 1.98). The strongest positive influence belongs to the reliability factor (X2): its coefficient equals 0.287, that is, holding the other factors constant, a one-point increase in the reliability score raises the competitiveness index by an average of 0.287 units. Responsiveness ranks second (X3, $\beta = 0.215$) and assurance third (X4, $\beta = 0.196$). Tangibles (X1) has the smallest, yet still significant, influence ($\beta = 0.118$).

The reliability of the model was confirmed by diagnostic tests. The VIF values for all factors range from 1.79 to 2.41, well below the critical threshold (10, or 5 in conservative assessment), meaning that no serious multicollinearity is present. The Durbin–Watson statistic equals 1.94, very close to 2, which indicates the absence of autocorrelation in the residuals. The result of the Breusch–Pagan test ($\chi^2 = 6.12$; $p = 0.295$) provides grounds to reject the hypothesis of heteroscedasticity, meaning that the residual variance is homogeneous (homoscedastic). Consequently, the OLS estimates are efficient, unbiased, and consistent.

To compare the relative contribution of the factors, standardized (beta) coefficients were also calculated. They likewise confirmed the order of importance of the variables: reliability (0.34) > responsiveness (0.26) > assurance (0.23) > empathy (0.17) > tangibles (0.15). This result is theoretically justified: for consumers, the reliable and prompt delivery of the promised service is of higher priority than the external appearance of the trade service.

A scenario (forecast) analysis was conducted on the basis of the model. If an enterprise increases its reliability score by one point (for example, from 3.5 to 4.5), the competitiveness index is expected to rise by 0.287 units, holding the other factors constant — that is, by approximately 47% relative to the mean value. Similarly, a one-point improvement in responsiveness raises the index by 0.215 units. These calculations enable management decisions to compare the expected return on resources allocated to each factor. Thus, hypotheses H1, H2, and H3

were empirically confirmed.

To evaluate the predictive accuracy of the model, an analysis of residuals was carried out. The distribution of the residuals was close to a normal distribution; the mean absolute error (MAE) amounted to 0.061 and the root mean square error (RMSE) to 0.074. These values are low relative to the mean value of the competitiveness index (0.612), showing that the model possesses sufficient accuracy for practical forecasting. No systematic pattern was observed in the dispersion of residuals relative to the fitted values, which additionally confirms the correctness of the model specification.

Based on the results of the analysis, a step-by-step mechanism for assessing the impact of trade service quality on competitiveness was proposed (Table 3). This mechanism divides the assessment process into sequential stages, from data collection to the formation of a management decision (Table 3).

Table 3. Step-by-Step Algorithm of the Econometric Assessment Mechanism

Stage	Content	Main tools and outcome
1	Data collection	SERVQUAL questionnaire, Likert scale; primary scores for the quality dimensions.
2	Indicator formation	Normalization of factors, calculation of the integral competitiveness index.
3	Modelling	OLS regression, estimation of coefficients (β , t , p).
4	Diagnostics	VIF, Durbin–Watson, Breusch–Pagan tests; verification of model adequacy.
5	Interpretation and decision	Identification of priority factors, channelling resources to the factors with the largest contribution.

The research results confirm the conclusions in the international literature regarding the positive relationship between service quality and competitiveness, while introducing an important refinement. The leading role of the reliability dimension has been noted many times in classical SERVQUAL studies; our findings also substantiated econometrically that precisely this factor has the largest marginal contribution. At the same time, the relatively weak yet statistically significant influence of the tangibles factor may indicate that, with the development of digital trade, the role of physical infrastructure in competition has partially diminished.

The practical significance of the obtained results lies in the fact that they enable the allocation of limited resources to the directions yielding the highest return. The magnitude of the coefficients helps managers assess approximately how much investment in a particular quality dimension will increase competitiveness. For example, measures aimed at improving reliability (systems for timely and error-free service delivery) are expected to yield a considerably higher return in terms of competitiveness than the renewal of physical equipment.

The limitations of the study should also be acknowledged. First, since the data were collected for a particular period and region, caution is required when generalizing the results to other markets. Second, the linear model does not fully capture the possible non-linear and interactive effects among the factors. In future research, the use of panel data, structural equation modelling (SEM), or non-linear specifications may further enhance the explanatory power of the model.

In addition, the proposed assessment mechanism is based on static cross-sectional data and does not account for changes in quality factors over time or for their lagged effects. The role of customer satisfaction and loyalty as mediating variables also deserves separate attention. These directions create a promising foundation for future research and provide an opportunity to enrich the mechanism with dynamic models.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the research, the impact of trade service quality indicators on the level of competitiveness was assessed quantitatively using econometric methods, and the following principal conclusions were reached. The five dimensions of service quality jointly explain 73.1% of the variation in competitiveness, which demonstrates the decisive role of the quality factor. The strongest influence belongs to the reliability and responsiveness factors, which constitute the priority direction for enhancing competitiveness.

The applied diagnostic tests (VIF, Durbin–Watson, Breusch–Pagan) confirmed that the model estimates are reliable, unbiased, and consistent. These results provide a sufficient statistical basis for the practical implementation of the assessment mechanism. The step-by-step algorithm proposed in the article enables trade enterprises to make decisions on quality management on a quantitative rather than an intuitive basis.

On the basis of the research results, the following practical recommendations were developed: first, it is

advisable for trade enterprises to channel their quality-management resources primarily towards improving the reliability and responsiveness dimensions, since these make the largest marginal contribution to competitiveness; second, it is recommended to monitor the quality indicators regularly (at least twice a year) and to update the parameters of the regression model; third, regional trade administration bodies may use this econometric mechanism as a benchmarking tool in assessing the competitiveness of enterprises. Econometric mechanisms for assessing the quality of trade services serve as an effective tool for managing enterprise competitiveness and, by channelling resources towards the factors with the highest return, contribute to ensuring a sustainable competitive advantage.

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